

Rendering Surface Properties Using a Dual-Purpose Soft Wearable Actuator

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Abstract. The aim of this study is to develop a soft wearable actuator capable of rendering surface shape and hardness. The system consists of an adjustable air source and two parallel inflatable balloons and is designed to be worn on the fingertip. By modulating the internal air pressure while the user moves across a surface, different surface properties can be simulated. Initial results obtained using a sinusoidal surface profile indicate that, with further development, the actuator is capable of successfully rendering surface geometry.

Keywords: Haptics, Wearable Device, Soft Actuator, Rendering.

1 Literature review

Numerous studies have addressed the rendering of surface properties such as texture, hardness/softness, stickiness/slipperiness, and temperature, commonly referred to as *surface haptics*. Other works combine multiple such cues and are therefore described as *multimodal tactile displays*. In many of these studies, the user's finger directly interacts with a physical surface. However, achieving multimodal surface rendering without the use of a wearable device remains highly challenging, and research in this direction is still ongoing. To address this challenge, several wearable approaches have been proposed. Yamamoto *et al.* developed a contact pad integrated into an electrostatic haptic display to render both texture and softness. Kyung *et al.* introduced a soft, fingertip-mountable tactile actuator based on a dielectric elastomer actuator, capable of generating normal forces on the fingertip. For applications such as virtual reality, Carpi *et al.* proposed a bubble-shaped electroactive polymer elastomer actuator to render force and displacement at the fingertip. In a different application context, Paik *et al.* developed a soft pneumatic actuator to generate surface contour cues through skin deformation.

2 Methodology

2.1 Soft Actuator

The developed dual-purpose soft wearable actuator is capable of providing three-dimensional surface perception. It employs two latex balloons to separately render

softness and surface shape, with the upper balloon responsible for softness cues and the lower balloon for shape rendering. The internal air pressure of each balloon is regulated using pressure and force sensor feedback. Both balloons share the same structural and control design. The overall structure of the device is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 The soft tactile actuator

2.2 Control Unit

As is seen in Fig. 2, the system employs two Arduino Uno microcontrollers. One Arduino is dedicated to controlling the force-sensitive resistor (FSR) sensor, while the second Arduino controls the solenoid valves and the pressure sensors. A miniature air pump (KPM12A-3C01) powered at 5 V is connected to the control Arduino and supplies pressurized air to the system. The pump is connected to a plastic tube that splits into two independent air paths. One path supplies the upper balloon to render softness sensations, while the second path supplies the lower balloon to render surface shape cues. Each path follows the same configuration: the air pump is followed by a 5 V solenoid valve, a flow restriction element, and a pressure sensor used to measure the internal air pressure before inflation of the balloon.

Fig. 2 Shows (a) Arduino UNO, (b) flow measure, (c) Air pump, (d) solenoid valve, (e) Soft actuator, (f) FSR sensor

3 Actuator Characterization

To render softness and surface profile, two key parameters are considered: actuator displacement and actuator stiffness (k). Experiments were conducted to characterize these parameters as a function of the applied air pressure, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The resulting relationships are summarized in Table 3.

Fig. 3 Shows the real different states of the actuator respectively with the amount of pumped air.

Table 1: Measured grows rate and force values exerted by the actuator

Valve timing ms (On/Off)	Grows Rate (mm)		Pressure (Kpa)		Force (mN)	
	Flow Rate 0.5L/min	Flow Rate 0.75L/min	Flow Rate 0.5L/min	Flow Rate 0.75L/min	Flow Rate 0.5L/min	Flow Rate 0.75L/min
100/200	2mm	3mm	3.46	5.43	170.03	280.32
200/200	3mm	4mm	5.45	7.58	278.18	381.06
500/200	4mm	6mm	7.62	11.23	380.95	497.87
1000/200	6mm	8mm	11.43	16.12	497.51	707.02
2000/200	8mm	max	16.22	17.52	706.84	770.89
3000/200	max	Risky	17.62	Risky	771.22	Risky

4 Initial Results

Applied force measured using FSR sensor for two different conditions. Fig. 4 shows the output of the measurement that in fact shows the surface profile. Softness was not involved in this case.

Fig. 4 The measurements obtained by the FSR sensor with 0.05s sampling time.

Aknowlegment

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